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“KAPLOMBAYOWAN A LENA”

Prince Bantogen took a rest under the shade of the tree Rani'ay a Rogong that is bending towards the water, exhaustedly looking for the place Lombayowan a Lena. Suddenly, he saw and asked an old man Kabagombongan i To' if he does know what this place called and what are those two resplendent buildings over a distant.

The old man explained that this place is called Lombatan, kingdom of Bolanen. He further described that the very big building is the Torogan of Petaedan who has a younger brother named Batara sa Rinayong and a beautiful sister who is called Sinangelay sa Mayag who keeps working on her embroidery or needlework. On the other side is the Torogan of Bolanen. There lived a beautiful princess named Dalondon sa Magayag, a sister of Sarigidan Malna-younger brother of Bolanen, who is always conscious about her looks no time for work and embroidery.

Prince Bantogen requested him to go and ask the young sister of Petaedan if she would allow me to pay a visit to send his respect. The old man agreed to fulfill his request. After a few moments, a tremendous and thunderbolt sound steps of numerous guards, holding their sharp spears, were heard. A royal procession took place where Sarigidan Malna was regally dressed, royal flags were raised, five-tiered royal umbrella held aloft, and finally gongs were beaten to be heard all around the sea. All of a sudden, everyone dazzled and noticed the handsome datu walking gracefully alone on the shore. At that moment, Sarigidan Malna ordered his guards to invite him come near to inquire some sort of questions daring that if he is not frightened, the two will become friends. As soon as possible, guards followed Bantogen and sounded their guns, shaking their shields, shouting at him, and pointing spears near him however, Bantogen remained calm, walking steadfast in a majestic way.

Around Sagadan was Sarigidan Malna who warned him that no one may enter Lombayowan a Lena unless he pays due respect to our customs or be killed at once. Now, the two datu began the big fight with their weapons clashed. Not long afterwards, a strong wind blew the tobaw covering the head of Bantugen. Sagadan was destructed and remembered what he heard that the only one who has golden flowers beneath black hair was no other than great Prince Bantugen of Bembaran so he decided to stop fighting, putting down his kampilan and kelong for the people of Bembaran and Lombatan both belong to the same clan, descended from Diwata Ndaw Gibon whom he considered him as new-found brother. Sarigidan Malna called his sister to serve betelnut to the handsome prince. Dalondon sa Magayag gave a sidelong glance, catching a glimpse of Bantugen while serving the betelnut quid so as the two have mutual understanding, played chessboard game together where Bantogen always championed, remained undefeated over her.

All of a sudden, a loud sound beating of gongs was heard in the resplendent torogan, the arrival of Misoyaw from Kadaan with a very beautiful princess Dalomabi ko Dinar he had captured, together with his maid Kilaman. This time, Bantogen was destructed and defeated five times on their chess game. Dalondon Pagayaw was puzzled and guessed that the captured beautiful princess was indeed his sweetheart. A victorious parade happened where troops of Misoyaw marched proudly. Sarigidan Malna asked prince Bantogen confirming if the captured princess was his sweetheart for he would not allow the captors to leave without freeing the princess.

The maidservant of the captured princess sensed a strange feeling that Bantogen is around because of the breeze of rare perfume that circulate the place. She informed the princess right away but the captured princess refuse to believe until she caught a direct look at prince Bantogen who grieved and struggled with sorrow but kept all his sorrow to himself.

The noisy parade which had passed the torogan of Sagadan had now arrived at the torogan of Petaeden where misoyaw proudly looked around addressing the king Bakolodan Gomogaw. A messenger was called to inform Sarigidan Malna to come to the royal wedding for his presence is needed. Finally, Sarigidan Malna was informed and invited Bantogen to go with him promising that he shall stay by his side in peace or war.

Sarigidan Malna talked formally to Misoyaw in agreement exchanging a whole town of Madem or one big camp of Manobos for Dalomabi ko Dinar. Misoyaw sneered at the offer. Sarigidan changed his offer to persuade more Misoyaw, his kampilan and shield instead but Misoyaw again refused so Misoyaw now faced the consequence for refusing these offers until such time, a messenger of Minalang from Kaibat a Kadaan arrived in the resplendent torogan informing Misoyaw that he has to return quickly for his kingdom has been invaded by Saronay sa Mimbala capturing all the ladies in the lamin of Kaibat a Kadaan. Misoyaw was shocked upon hearing this, trapped in between fire and ice for he could not escape directly since Sarigidan Malna would not allow him to do so.